

Dynamo

Dynamic Spatio-Temporal Modulation
of Light by Phononic Architectures.

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D4.4: Spatio-temporal maps of optimal twisted samples

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WP4. T.4.3: Sample characterization

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Dynamo Spatio-temporal maps of optimal twisted samples

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4. Introduction

4.1. Executive Summary

The present document relates to the development of Deliverable 4.4: Spatio-temporal maps of optimal twisted samples.

It covers the experimental details on the acquisition of full spatio-temporal maps of the vibrational state of several phononic crystal samples with different degrees of complexity, which were used to guide and determine the final designs of the samples to be used in Dynamo.

4.2. Relation to Other Project Documents

The present deliverable is related to the following documents:

- Deliverable 3.3 Optimal twisted phononic crystal plate based on hole array membranes.
- Deliverable 4.2: High frequency characterization set-up.

4.3. Abbreviation List

This is the list of the acronyms that are used in the present document:

- Signal-to-noise ratio (SNR)
- Two-dimensional Fast Fourier Transform (2D-FFT)
- Surface Acoustic Waves (SAWs)

4.4. Reference Documents

1. Tachizaki, T. *et al.* Scanning ultrafast Sagnac interferometry for imaging two-dimensional surface wave propagation. *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* **77**, 043713 (2006).
2. Cuffe, J. *et al.* Phonons in Slow Motion: Dispersion Relations in Ultrathin Si Membranes. *Nano Lett.* **12**, 3569–3573 (2012).

5. Spatio-temporal maps of optimal twisted samples

5.1. Twisted samples

During the project, we have explored several sample designs with the objective to build samples with a rich response both in the spectral and spatial dimensions (i.e., strong oscillations with very different frequencies along large spatial regions). Our approach to achieve that goal has been to design phononic crystals by structuring a substrate with micrometric features (typically micrometric holes). The spatial features of these structures ultimately determine the acoustic response of the sample, whether it be its vibrational spectrum or the spatial distribution of vertical displacements over the surface. While creating regular structures is relatively easy from the technical point of view and the theoretical models can provide very good predictions on sample response (which is crucial for design pipelines), these simple designs tend to generate quite simple acoustic responses. For example, in Figure 1, we show that a square lattice provides very good acoustic response, i.e., strong surface displacements and very high

signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) on the signals acquired by using the picosecond ultrasonic technique¹. However, a deeper look into this result shows that the design is not very well suited for the desired objectives. If one studies the surface displacements over the

Figure 1. Square lattice phononic crystal. Left panel: sample reflectivity map of a phononic crystal built over a silicon substrate by regularly placing a square array of holes with a period of 5 microns, a diameter of 2.5 microns, and a hole depth of 5 microns. The image covers a field of view of 200×200 microns. Right panel: spatio-temporal scan of the sample along the vertical black line shown in the left panel. For each point along the line (horizontal axis on the graph), the sample is probed with different delays between the pump pulse (that excites the acoustic response of the sample) and the probe pulse (that measures the surface displacement).

preferred directions of the crystal, the dispersion curves of the structure can be experimentally studied. The red and blue straight diagonal lines that can be clearly seen on the spatio-temporal map are the signature of a nearly lineal dispersion relation of the fundamental surface acoustic mode.

By taking a two-dimensional Fast Fourier Transform (2D-FFT), it is possible to calculate the dispersion curve of this fundamental mode. This can be seen on Figure 2. Whereas this matches the expected behaviour of a regular structured sample, in order for this result to be useful for the light modulation objectives in Dynamo the dispersion relations of the samples should present richer information, either by showing a more complex behaviour (i.e., non-linear), or by the excitation of additional vibrational modes (i.e., more

Figure 2. Experimental dispersion curve along the ΓY direction of the phononic crystal shown in Figure 1.

than one branch should be clearly visible on the spatio-temporal maps or in the dispersion curves).

One way to reach the desired complexity is to break the regular structure of the phononic crystal. This can be achieved by many ways, such as by introducing defects in the structure, by varying the diameter and depth of a fraction of the holes, or by creating a twisted phononic crystal. This last approach seems particularly practical, as its only requirement is to overlap two identical lattices and rotate one with respect to the other for a fixed angle.

The resulting structure from this approach is shown in Figure 3, where it can clearly be seen that the introduction of even a small rotation completely changes the spatial distribution of holes along the surface, generating semi-periodic structures (typically known as Moiré patterns) that could show more complex dispersion relations.

Figure 3. Surface reflectivity for a twisted phononic crystal. The resulting structure is generated by introducing a 2.5° rotation angle between two square lattices with the same parameters as the shown before (5 microns lattice parameter, 2.5 microns hole diameter, and 5 microns hole depth). The image covers a field of view of 160×160 microns.

However, when trying to excite Surface Acoustic Waves (SAWs) in this structure, we found several experimental hurdles. The main problem is that, even though the features of the structure are well suited to the optical parameters of our setup (i.e., we can focus the pump beam easily inside the structure, and the surface has a very high optical quality which provides high light reflectivity for the probe beam), we found that the central frequency of our SAWs (which is centered around 1 GHz) cannot propagate inside the crystal for long distances. This can be clearly seen in Figure 5. In the first image, which corresponds to the excitation of SAWs over a flat sample (without any holes), it is possible to see the waves travelling through the surface as concentric rings around the position of the pump (the center of the image). However, the same study for the twisted samples shows no clear SAW propagation over distances longer than just a few microns, indicating that the waves stop propagating along the surface after a few interactions with the holes.

Figure 5. Surface displacement snapshots for fixed delay times between pump and probe. All images correspond to a field of view of 160×160 microns. Left: Surface displacement of a flat sample (without any hole structure) 3 ns after the arrival of the pump. Middle: Surface displacement on the twisted sample 1 ns after the arrival of the pump. Right: Surface displacement on the twisted sample 3 ns after the arrival of the pump.

Similar behavior can be seen for samples with different twist angles. Figure 4 shows the results of the same study applied to a sample with a twist angle of 10° . Again, SAWs can only be found very close to the excitation source, and no surface displacements are found over large distances.

Figure 4. Twisted sample with a rotation angle of 10° . First two images correspond to a field of view of 160×160 microns, second image is an 80×80 microns zoom inside the black square region. Left: Reflectivity image of the surface. Middle: Surface displacement 2 ns after the arrival of the pump pulse. Right: Surface displacement 3 ns after the arrival of the pump pulse.

Figure 6. Calculated dispersion curves for two different phononic crystals, one with a regular square grid, and another with a twist angle of 5° . The calculated results delineate the sound cone, represented by the off-white area in the band diagrams. The latter establishes the substrate's smallest phase velocity within the irreducible Brillouin zone (Γ , X, M, Γ). Insets show different surface acoustic modes below the sound cone.

These results have been confirmed by numerical simulations of the structures, as shown in Figure 6. For the regular crystal with a square lattice, the dispersion curves show propagating modes in the frequency range between a few MHz and 1 GHz. However, for the twisted samples the allowed frequencies lay in a much smaller frequency range, far from the experimental range provided by the setup. This implies that all the waves that the setup can generate (around 1GHz in frequency) escape into the substrate (radiative zone) and do not generate any surface displacement, which is the only information the system can detect.

5.2. Thin membranes

The latest results for the Moiré patterns reveal the difficulty in achieving significant displacement and, as a consequence, a strong elastic wave. In an effort to improve the absolute value of displacement and to obtain a richer frequency content, we have shifted our focus to thin film configurations, specifically membranes.

As noted in the literature², the dispersion relations of hypersonic acoustic phonons in free-standing membranes exhibit a richer frequency content. A reduction in the phase and group velocities of the fundamental flexural mode is observed when compared to bulk values. The absolute value of displacement is higher because the elastic energy remains confined in the membrane for a longer duration, with leaks occurring only at the borders rather than into a substrate, as is the case with surface acoustic waves propagating in a semi-infinite space.

The fabrication of a 500 nm thick membrane in SiN was carried out by partners at ICMA. Our interest in silicon nitride is based on its well-known material properties, the unrivalled control of its nanofabrication and its still unchallenged supremacy as the material for micro-nano-electronic and MEMS devices. A 50 nm layer of gold on top of the membrane is necessary to measure the displacement using our interferometry-based technique. The structure under study is depicted in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Membrane geometry.

As described above, the current configuration of the experimental setup allows for the detection of surface acoustic waves within a field of view exceeding 200 square microns in reasonable time (10 minutes). This field of view has been achieved over the past few months and represents a significant technological advancement compared to existing setups in other laboratories. This recent progress allows us to plot the dispersion curves

of the sample in just a few minutes, a feat that was not possible before. Consequently, the precision of the measurements has become outstanding. Within this short timeframe, the signal scan is extremely clean, requiring no filtering or image processing.

The temporal scan of the signal outside the membrane, presented in Figure 8, follows the typical pattern of a Rayleigh wave in a semi-infinite space. However, the signal detected in the membrane region is completely different and exhibits a complex frequency content (Figure 9). We note a new frequency component in the signal that persists for a long duration (see the time scale between 2000 and 6000 ps).

Figure 8. Temporal signal measured outside of the membrane region.

Figure 9. Temporal signal measured inside of the membrane region.

To study the sample in detail and properly analyze the frequency content, we performed a complete scan of the surface at a fixed time delay of 2000 ps (Figure 10). The increase in mode frequencies and their spacing when transitioning to a membrane configuration is clearly observed. The optimized setup allows for the investigation of acoustic modes over a large field of view, enabling observations of in-plane propagation and dispersion relations. For the dispersion curve, we scanned both in time and along the line as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Spatial scanning of out-of-plane displacement at a fixed delay-line position ($t = 2000$ ps). The black line represents the path of the spatio-temporal scan using for plotting dispersion curves.

As result of scan along the line, Figure 11 shows a very clear signal of surface acoustic wave in time and in space in a non-contact, non-destructive manner. Figure 12 presents the direct Fourier transform of the spatio-temporal map.

Figure 11. Spatio-temporal scan of the membrane surface.

Regarding the obtained dispersion curve for Surface Acoustic Waves (SAW) in the membrane (Figure 13), the most notable feature is the quadratic dispersion of the flexural mode extending beyond the 2 GHz range. The signal is robust and clear, allowing for precise extraction of group velocity values with high accuracy. Thanks to the remarkable precision of measurement, it has become possible to observe another branch of the dispersion curve, the dilatational mode. These measurements show a good agreement with the theoretical dispersion curves, shown in Figure 14.

Figure 12. Direct Fourier Transform of the spatio-temporal scan on the membrane surface.

Figure 13. Measured dispersion relation of surface acoustic waves in a thin membrane. The two yellow curves represent to two different branches, one corresponding to the flexural mode (red arrow) and a second corresponding to the dilatational mode (green arrow).

Figure 14. Comparison between experimental measurements and theoretical calculations for the dispersion curves of a flat membrane. Blue and red dots correspond to the theoretical values for the A0 and S0 modes, respectively.

6. Conclusion

While the twisted samples seemed like a promising venue for generating rich spatio-spectral responses in a controlled manner, our first trials have shown that the first designs only allow low frequency waves to propagate, which are not easy to generate and measure by using the picosecond ultrasonics technique. Following designs will be built with different feature sizes, accommodating the response to the sweet spot of the experimental technique.

As a backup strategy, we have started working on thin films, that show promising results both in spectral and spatial response, with waves propagating in the full experimental range of the technique. This study not only motivates us to explore membranes further for investigating artificial materials, but also anticipates potential future applications requiring high amplitude and long-duration vibrations due to the remarkably low phase and group velocities. Quantitative simulation of intensities in spectra and the assessment of modified dispersion effects on phonon lifetimes, including the evaluation of group velocity, are currently under investigation.